

Factors Influencing the Achievement of Sustainable Performance of Manufacturing Companies

(Case Study at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk)

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Abstract:- Manufacturing company activities touch with social and environmental aspects. PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk, a manufacturing company since 2021, has chosen steps to strengthen a sustainable corporate strategy. The research objective was to determine the effect of Green Organizational Culture and Green Knowledge Management on Corporate Sustainability Performance with Employee Green Behavior as an intervening variable. This research was conducted on 193 permanent employees as respondents. Quantitative research with survey methods. SEM-PLS data analysis using SmartPLS 3 software. The study's results, Green Organizational Culture, influences Employee Green Behavior and Corporate Sustainability Performance. Likewise, Green Knowledge Management influences Employee Green Behavior and Corporate Sustainability Performance. It was also found that Employee Green Behavior did not affect Corporate Sustainability Performance. Then when each of the Green Organizational Culture and Green Knowledge Management through Employee Green behavior does not influence Corporate Sustainability Performance, it is concluded that Green Organizational Culture and Green Knowledge Management can be determining factors for developing Employee Green Behavior and achieving Corporate Sustainability Performance targets. The cause of Employee Green Behavior not influencing Corporate Sustainability Performance is the Covid-19 pandemic, with social restrictions in activities reducing the role of employees in sustainability programs.

Keywords:- Corporate Sustainability Performance, Green Organizational Culture, Green Knowledge Management, Employee Green Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since 2015, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) has announced the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a call to the international community to end poverty, make tangible efforts to safeguard the planet and aim for everyone to enjoy peace and prosperity by 2030. The call includes 17 targets that must be met for everyone to benefit from sustainable development. One of these aims is Responsible Consumption and Production, which includes

activities such as all countries actively participating in sustainable consumption and production.

In general, the manufacturing industry is critical to economic growth. However, some risks can develop in this area that must be addressed, given that this sector's operational activities are inextricably linked to using hazardous materials and technology. As a result, it has the potential to pose environmental concerns, such as the hazardous waste generated. As a result, this sector frequently receives media attention and even social pressure from the community, such as rallies near the company's operations (Nuryanto et al., 2020). As a result, sustainability and corporate responsibility are increasingly being recognized as a concept that provides a way of thinking and acting that directs companies toward a sustainable business that is carried out effectively, thereby uproviding benefits that have a positive impact on business, society, and the environment (Camilleri, 2017). Ehnert et al. (2014) believe that ethical performance factors (economic, environmental, and social) might provide a valuable framework for executing sustainable business decisions.

PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk has decided to boost its sustainability approach since 2021, according to a Message from the Board of Directors. Of course, the future strategy set will continue to adapt to the company's sustainability context, which focuses on increasing collaboration with local communities, reducing carbon emissions and energy conversion, recycling water in the manufacturing process, and developing climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies.

Based on the results of pre-research on 21 employees, three variables were obtained that were considered influential on Corporate Sustainability Performance, namely Green Organizational Culture, Green Knowledge Management, and Green Employee Behavior. Based on research conducted by Magsi et al. (2018), reinforced by Fok et al.'s research (2020), states that the effect of Green Organizational Culture is significant on Corporate Sustainability. However, the research results by Santosa and Nawangsari (2021) state that Green Organizational Culture has no influence on Corporate Sustainability. Furthermore, based on the research of Abbas and Sagsan (2019), which is reinforced by the research of Shahzad et al. (2020), as well

as the research of Noor and Nawangsari (2021), there is a significant influence of Knowledge Management on Corporate Sustainability. Meanwhile, research, according to Afqarina and Dihan (2018), Knowledge Management does not affect Economic Performance, one of the dimensions of Sustainability Performance. In addition, research conducted by Sulistio & Dianawati (2020) on manufacturing companies states that there is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management through Environmental Innovation Behavior on Firm Performance. Meanwhile, Polas et al. (2021) found that knowledge management through intervening in Employee Environment Awareness affect Environmental Sustainability. Then the results of research from Sudaryati et al. (2020) showed that Environment-base Behavior as mediation of Environment-base Culture does not have a significant effect on Company Performance. Meanwhile, Lee (2020) research found that Employee Behavior as a mediation of Corporate Ethic Value also influences Corporate Sustainability. A research gap in previous research makes this research even more interesting to study further.

II. THEORITICAL REVIEW

A. Corporate Sustainability Performance

Sutawidjaya et al. (2022) define *sustainability* as a process of long-term development that takes place on three levels: environmental protection, economic growth, and social equity. At the same time, these three characteristics are frequently referred to as the "triple bottom line," which is used to assess the performance of certain development initiatives or projects.

Corporate sustainability entails balancing environmental protection, social welfare, and economic prosperity while pursuing long-term success goals for the company's and its stakeholders' health. A sustainable organization transparently fulfills these responsibilities, and each stakeholder is accountable for the performance results obtained (Ferver, 2019).

B. Green Organizational Culture

Green Organizational Culture, as defined by Bertassini et al. (2021), is an organizational culture that encourages every employee to promote and carry out sustainable circular

activities to gain a competitive advantage with aims aligned with the company's goals.

According to Tahir et al. (2019), Green Organizational Culture is a culture of sustainability in which organizational employees share assumptions and attitudes about the significance of balancing environmental responsibility, economic efficiency, and social justice.

C. Green Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is the selection of a knowledge strategy and strategic decisions in managing knowledge potential via a knowledge management process that involves knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, development, maintenance, and application, where this is supplemented by an evaluation of knowledge strategy application (Raudeliūnienė et al. 2018).

According to Gauthier and Zhang (2020), Green Knowledge Management is the process of consolidating knowledge through the generalization of ideas from each individual, followed by the development of all initiatives from stakeholders, and concluded by reintegrating sustainability strategies with existing strategies. In this case, the process is extremely important in preserving the environment.

D. Employee Green Behavior

Employee Green Behavior, as defined by Yanti and Nawangsari (2021), is the behavior of employees who care about the environment in the form of attitudes of employees who pay attention to the condition of the surrounding environment and try to play a role in improving the situation by preserving the environment, such as conserving resources and reducing waste in the manufacturing process.

Meanwhile, Farooq et al. (2021) define Employee Green Behavior as "employee behavior that demonstrates sustainability behavior in their daily lives, in which Employees complete tasks demanded by the organization with an emphasis on sustainability aspects."

This research's hypothesis is based on the theoretical study presented in the literature review; the research's conceptual framework is as follows (Figure 1).

Hypothesis:

H1: Green Organizational Culture -> Employee Green Behavior

H2: Green Knowledge Management -> Employee Green Behavior

H3: Green Organizational Culture -> Corporate Sustainability Performance

H4: Green Knowledge Management -> Corporate Sustainability Performance

H5: Employee Green Behavior -> Corporate Sustainability Performance

H6: Green Organizational Culture -> Employee Green Behaviour -> Corporate Sustainability Performance

H7: Green Knowledge Management -> Employee Green Behaviour -> Corporate Sustainability Performance

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

In this study, quantitative research was used. According to Kasmir (2022), quantitative research is used to prove a theory, whether it is the influence or relationship of a variable. The survey research method was employed in this study, and according to Kasmir (2022), survey research is research conducted on a population and then employing sample data from that population. In survey research, the sample must be homogeneous so that the research results can be more targeted.

B. Population and Sample

In this study, the population consisted of 370 employees in the Head Office (head office) with a homogeneous working period of at least 1 (one year). Then the sampling method used is Nonprobability Sampling -

purposive sampling, a sample selection technique that does not provide the entire population equal opportunities to become research samples (Kasmir, 2022). based on the calculation of the Slovin formula, the sample in this study was obtained from as many as 193 employees.

C. Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method used in this study is SEM-PLS, meaning that researchers use the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method with the instrument testing method using Partial Least Square (PLS). According to Noor (2017), SEM analysis is a hybrid model that incorporates two models in its application: (1) Structural Model, a model with exogenous and endogenous latent variables. (2) Measurement Model (model as an indicator of exogenous and endogenous factors). The software used to process the research data is SmartPLS version 3.2.9.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Outer Model

A test is performed in the measurement model test (outer model), particularly validity and reliability tests utilizing the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) technique. Each test on the measurement model (outer model) is explained below.

Fig 2 Outer Model Testing

Based on Figure 2, which is the result of the Convergent Validity Test with Outer Loading, shows the outer loading value of each indicator in the variables Green Organizational Culture (X1), Green Knowledge Management (X2), Employee Green Behavior (X3), and Corporate Sustainability Performance. value > 0.7 (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). This indicates that all indicators of the variables in this study are valid.

Discriminant Validity test with *Fornell-Lecker* (Table 1), a measurement method that suggests comparing the square root value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each latent variable with the correlation between other latent variables in the model (Hair et al., 2021). it was found that the AVE root value of each variable with the variable itself is greater than the correlation value with other variables. So the model is said to have a good discriminant validity value.

Table 1 Fornell-Larcker Value of Research Variables

Variabel	Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	Green Organizational Culture (X1)	Green Knowledge Management (X2)	Employee Green Behaviour (X3)
Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.789			
Green Organizational Culture (X1)	0.590	0.771		
Green Knowledge Management (X2)	0.546	0.661	0.801	
Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	0.394	0.585	0.524	0.779

Source: Processed From Primary Data Using Smartpls 3.2.9

In this study, the next step is if the validity test is met, using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) criteria (Table 2). The criterion value for Cronbach's alpha is > 0.7, and for composite reliability (CR) is > 0.7. (Hair et al, 2021) it was found that all variables produced Cronbach's alpha values greater than 0.7 and produced composite reliability (CR) values greater than 0.7. It was concluded that the model met the criteria for the value of the research model, which was declared to have reliability in measuring its variables.

Table 2 Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Result
Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.878	0.908	Reliable
Green Organizational Culture (X1)	0.902	0.921	Reliable
Green Knowledge Management (X2)	0.953	0.959	Reliable
Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	0.927	0.939	Reliable

B. Inner Model

Testing the inner model was carried out to see whether the relationship between latent variables, namely exogenous and endogenous constructs, could provide answers to questions regarding the relationship between latent variables that had been previously hypothesized (Hair et al. 2021). The structural model test is seen from 3 kinds of values, namely by looking at the R Square and R Square values Adjusted, Predictive Relevance (Q²), and the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value (Ghozali & Latan, 2021).

Testing the coefficient of determination (R²) is a way to assess how much endogenous variables can be explained by exogenous variables. The coefficient of determination (R²) is expected to be between 0 and 1. Testing the coefficient of determination aims to measure the ability of the model to explain the variance of the endogenous (dependent) variables. The R Square analysis (R²) performed on each endogenous latent variable shows the

magnitude of the level of influence received by the endogenous latent variable from each exogenous variable contributing to it (Hair et al. 2021).

Based on the data in Table 3, the relationship between variables based on the R Square value can be explained that the Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y) variable is 0.442. This shows that 44.2% of the Corporate Sustainability Performance variable is influenced by the Green Organizational Culture (X1) variable, Green Knowledge Management (X2), and Employee Green Behavior (X3) simultaneously. Other variables beyond those studied influence the remaining 66.8%. The relationship between variables in Employee Green Behavior (X3) is 0.422, which means that 42.2% is influenced by the variables Green Organizational Culture (X1) and Green Knowledge Management (X2) simultaneously. In comparison, other variables beyond those studied influence the remaining 57.8%.

Table 3 R Square Value (R²)

Variabel	R Square (R ²)	R Square Adjusted
Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.442	0.433
Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	0.422	0.416

Source: Processed from primary data using SmartPLS 3.2.9

Cross-validated redundancy (Q²) or the Q-square test should be used to determine predictive relevance (Table 4). Q² > 0 shows that the model has real predictive relevance to particular variables, whereas Q² 0 (zero) implies that the model lacks predictive relevance. Predictive relevance ratings of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 suggest that the research

model is weak, moderate, and strong, respectively (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). Based on the data in Table 4, it can be seen that the Predictive Relevance (Q²) value is greater than 0 (zero), which indicates that the model is said to be accurate and good.

Table 4 Predictive Relevance Value (Q²)

Variabel	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	1158.000	857.207	0.237
Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	1930.000	1464.152	0.220

Source: Processed from primary data using SmartPLS 3.2.9

Goodness of Fit (GoF) Testing To validate the performance of the combination of the measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model), it can be obtained through the following calculations:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.615 \times 0.432}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.266}$$

GoF = 0.515

According to Ghazali and Latan (2021), the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) has three values: small = 0.1, medium = 0.25, and big = 0.36. The Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) calculated in this study is 0.515, indicating that the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) as a whole is good because the value of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) is more significant than 0.36 (large category GoF scale).

C. Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis test can be calculated from the Path Coefficient value, namely the T-statistic value of the relationship between variables in the study (Table 5).

Table 5 Path coefficient value, T statistic, and P-value

Variabel	Coefficient	T statistic	P-value	Result
Direct Effect				
Green Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	0.424	4.651	0.000	Significant positive influence
Green Knowledge Management (X2) -> Employee Green Behaviour (X3)	0.243	2.993	0.003	Significant positive influence
Green Organizational Culture (X1) -> Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.400	4.075	0.000	Significant positive influence
Green Knowledge Management (X2) -> Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.273	3.508	0.000	Significant positive influence
Employee Green Behaviour (X3) -> Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.017	0.240	0.811	It has no significant positive effect
Indirect Effect				
Green Organizational Culture (X1) -> Employee Green Behaviour (X3) -> Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.020	0.409	0.829	It has no significant positive effect
Green Knowledge Management (X2) -> Employee Green Behaviour (X3) -> Corporate Sustainability Performance (Y)	0.013	0.459	0.814	It has no significant positive effect

➤ Based on the Results, it can be Concluded that the Evaluation Result in this Research:

- Based on the hypothesis testing results, Green Organizational Culture has a significant positive effect on Employee Green Behavior at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This explains that the application of Green Organizational Culture, especially in terms of Employee Empowerment that the company has carried out, will affect Employee Green Behavior. These results can be interpreted that a good Green Organizational Culture will form employee behavior that is more aware of the environment and aspects related to sustainability. This follows what Farooq et al. (2021) conveyed: sustainability-oriented behavior is everyday behavior that is aware of aspects of sustainability, especially in carrying out tasks demanded by the organization. The findings of this study are consistent with prior research by Muisyo et al. (2020), who showed that Green Organizational Culture and the dimensions contained

within it have a substantial influence on the sustainable behavior of employees in a company. Furthermore, according to Hooi et al. (2022), regular implementation of Green Culture can have a beneficial and significant influence on boosting employee knowledge of environmentally friendly behavior.

- Based on the hypothesis testing results, Green Knowledge Management has a significant positive effect on Employee Green Behavior at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This explains the application of Green Knowledge Management. The optimal implementation of Green Knowledge Management can shape the behavior of employees who are more aware of sustainability aspects. Yu et al. (2022) believe Green Knowledge Management can provide a way for individuals within the organization to acquire knowledge from internal and external channels, which are then developed according to organizational conditions. The findings from this study are also consistent with previous research conducted by Safari et al. (2018), which found that

Green Knowledge has a significant effect on Green Behavior. Apart from that, these results also follow the research of Rubel et al. (2021) that Green Knowledge Management has a positive and significant effect on the formation of Green Behavior.

- Based on the results of hypothesis testing, there is a significant positive effect between Green Organizational Culture on Corporate Sustainability Performance at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This explains that implementing the Green Organizational Culture that the company has carried out will affect Corporate Sustainability Performance. So it can be interpreted that the implementation of a good Green Organizational Culture will have an impact on achieving a good company's sustainable performance as well. This is the opinion of Bertasini et al. (2021), which suggests that the Green Organizational Culture will encourage every employee to promote and carry out sustainable circular activities to achieve a competitive advantage with goals that align with the company's goals. The results of this study are also in line with previous research conducted by Magsi et al. (2018), which explained that Organizational Culture has a positive and significant influence on a company's Sustainability Performance. Likewise, the research results by Garcia-Machado et al. (2019) showed that Green Culture determines the achievement of Sustainability Performance because of its positive and significant relationship.
- The results of testing the following hypothesis show a significant positive effect between Green Knowledge Management on Corporate Sustainability Performance at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This explains that the implementation of Green Knowledge Management, especially those that the company has carried out, will affect Corporate Sustainability Performance. Yu et al. (2022) state that through Green Knowledge Management, companies are encouraged to have an efficient mechanism for storing knowledge in an organized manner so that it can be easily retrieved for future use. The results of this study are also per previous research from Abbas (2019) that all Knowledge Management dimensions simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on Organizational Sustainability Performance. Then it is also, the research results conducted by Noor and Nawangsari (2021), who researched a company in Indonesia and showed that Knowledge Management positively and significantly affects Sustainability Performance.
- Based on the results of testing the hypothesis that Employee Green Behavior has no significant positive effect on Corporate Sustainability Performance at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This means that the green behavior shown by current employees has yet to influence the achievement of the company's sustainable performance. This is in line with research conducted by Visser (2022), which results that the relationship between Environment Concern Behavior does not affect the achievement of a company's Environment Performance.

- Based on the results of testing the hypothesis that Green Organizational Culture through Employee Green has no significant positive effect on Corporate Sustainability Performance at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This means that applying a green culture that is manifested through the green behavior of employees currently only significantly influences the achievement of the company's sustainable performance. This is also in line with the results of research conducted by Sudaryati et al. (2020), who conducted research in manufacturing companies and found that Environment-base Behavior as a mediation of Environment-base Culture did not significantly affect Company Performance.
- Based on the results of testing the hypothesis that Green Knowledge Management through Employee Green Behavior has no significant positive effect on Corporate Sustainability Performance at PT Mulia Industrindo Tbk. This means that the management of green knowledge manifested through employees' green behavior only significantly influences achieving the company's sustainable performance. This study's results align with research conducted by Sulistio and Dianawati (2020) on manufacturing companies, which stated that there is no significant relationship between Knowledge Management through Environmental Innovation Behavior on Firm Performance.

V. CONCLUSION

➤ *Based on the results of data analysis, research discussion, and proof of the hypothesis, the researcher can draw the following conclusions:*

- Green Organizational Culture Influences Employee Green Behavior, meaning that if Green Organizational Culture can be implemented optimally, then Employee Green Behavior will grow well in every employee.
- Green Knowledge Management Influences Employee Green Behavior. If Green Knowledge Management can be implemented optimally, then Employee Green Behavior will grow well in every employee.
- Green Organizational Culture influences Corporate Sustainability Performance, meaning that if Green Organizational Culture can be implemented optimally, it can increase the achievement of Corporate Sustainability Performance.
- Green Knowledge Management Influences Corporate Sustainability Performance. Meaning that if Green Knowledge Management can be implemented optimally, it can increase the achievement of Corporate Sustainability Performance.
- Employee Green Behavior does not affect Corporate Sustainability Performance. This means that the current condition of Employee Green Behavior has a minor impact on achieving Corporate Sustainability Performance. And among the things considered the weakest are the conditions that have not grown evenly among employees in the waste sorting movement held by the company. As well as the emergence of personal awareness in making improvements aimed at cost efficiency in the work process. This is due to the not

optimal role of employees in efforts to achieve sustainable performance because the Covid-19 pandemic that hit has limited the natural part of employees in programs run by the company.

- Green Organizational Culture through Employee Green Behavior does not significantly influence the Company's Sustainability Performance. This means that the various Green Organizational Culture programs implemented so far with the intervention of Employee Green Behavior do not support the Corporate Sustainability Performance target policy. The main thing that is considered weak is related to the company's efforts to encourage increased company performance under the company's vision and mission, including the sustainability aspect.
- Green Knowledge Management through Employee Green Behavior does not significantly influence Corporate Sustainability Performance. This means that the various steps to develop Green Knowledge Management with the intervention of Employee Green Behavior do not significantly impact achieving the target of Corporate Sustainability Performance. The main thing still considered weak is related to the company's efforts to develop employee capabilities through training to increase sustainable competitiveness.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the discussion analysis and some of the conclusions above, suggestions that can be submitted to complement the research results and as material for consideration in the hope of providing constructive improvements for the company are as follows:

- The company consistently commits to carrying out Corporate Sustainability Performance to preserve the environment. Continue to raise employee awareness through ISO 14001:2015 Awareness training and form cadres of ISO 14001:2015 Internal Auditors who will ensure that each clause of ISO 14001:2015 can work properly.
- In terms of the company's Green Organizational Culture, a concrete step is needed from the company to achieve better Corporate Sustainability Performance, which is considered to be running well at this time to be continuously maintained and improved, such as setting performance targets for each function and employees related to efforts to reduce the impact on the environment, for example by providing Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for energy efficiency, use of alternative fuels, and cost efficiency for each function and individual employees. As well as providing an opportunity for every employee to solve problems related to efforts to reduce the environmental impact through the Quality Control Group (QCC).
- In terms of Green Knowledge Management, the company needs to take concrete steps to continue to impact achieving the target of Corporate Sustainability Performance. This can be done by maintaining and continuing to develop efforts to document the knowledge possessed by employees. This can be developed by implementing e-learning which can make

it easier for employees to access knowledge without being limited by space and time.

- The aspect of Employee Green Behavior. The company already has capital, namely the attitude of employees who care about the environment, namely pro-ecological employee behavior that is quite good, so that it can continue to be maintained through environmental care and preservation programs such as the "Waste Bank" movement, namely by educating and opening shelters for collecting recyclable waste in the employee's home environment, predominantly residential neighborhoods inhabited by the majority of employees. In addition, some things still need to be improved, namely, the "Waste Sorting Movement" program that is currently running needs to be evaluated for its implementation, especially related to employee participation in the program. The motivation of employees to participate in these activities must slowly be shifted from being oriented toward the prizes offered to the awareness and personal initiative of the employees.
- This research has limitations in carrying out data collection because this research was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic. Hence, regulations limiting interaction with respondents became an obstacle due to the need for a briefing process for respondents before filling out the questionnaire. Related to this, it is suggested that in the subsequent study, the implementation of data collection should be held directly to the respondents so that there is good interaction between the researchers and the respondents, as well as an explanation regarding the aims and objectives of the research, can be more clearly conveyed so that the respondents can provide a response that is following the objectives study.

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